

Budapest University of Technology and Economics
Faculty of Natural Sciences
Institute of Mathematics

Word and graph embedding for detecting anti-vaxxers in social media

BACHELOR THESIS

Author

Rita Csoma

Advisors

András Benczúr

Ferenc Béres

József Mala

May 21, 2021

Kivonat

A szakdolgozatom célja két eltérő beágyazási módszer bemutatása egy jelenleg aktuális praktikus példán keresztül. A Covid-19 világjárvány új kihívások elé állította az emberiséget. Az egyik ezen társadalmi kérdések közül a vakcina szkepticizmus. Dolgozatomban az internetről gyűjtött nyilvános rövid bejegyzéseken végeztem gépi tanulással osztályozást. Ennek célja a bejegyzés vakcina támogató vagy vakcina ellenes hozzáállásának meghatározása.

Részletesen bemutatásra kerül az ehhez használt két megközelítés valamint az azokkal elért eredmények. Egyrészt természetes nyelvfeldolgozás segítségével, a bejegyzések szövegét felhasználva, kétféle vektorizáló algoritmussal. Másrészt a bejegyzések közti relációkból épített gráf beágyazásával. Végül mindkét beágyazás kimenetét használva többféle osztályozó segítségével hasonlítottam össze a beágyazásokat.

Abstract

The purpose of this thesis is to discuss the applicability of two different embedding methods through a current practical example. Humanity faces new challenges due to the COVID-19 pandemic. One of these social issues is vaccine skepticism. In my thesis, I used machine learning algorithms for classification on public posts collected from the internet. The goal of this classification is to identify whether a post has a vaccine supporting or opposing attitude.

Two approaches are described and the results they yielded are shown in detail. One of these is natural language processing on the textual contents of the posts and encoded them as vectors using two different algorithms. The other is building a graph from the posts and relations between them and using a graph embedding method to map these graphs to fixed-size vector representations. Finally, I used different classification algorithms to compare the effectiveness of both approaches.

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Kivonat

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Outlining the problem

Vaccination was a controversial topic for a long time. With the Covid-19 pandemic outbreak at the end of 2019, the topic is more important than ever. Only a year after the first international cases were registered, multiple vaccines were developed and passed clinical testing. It is a record time compared to previous vaccines.

By the end of 2020, many countries are looking forward to vaccinating their citizens. It is still in question how many shots will be available and by when. Even if there is enough organizing mass vaccination is an enormous logistical challenge. Besides all these problems it seems that another factor might play a significant role in the fight against the pandemic. There are some people who are hesitant to get vaccinated, or even state that they will refuse any vaccine offered to them. Two groups of people commonly referred to as

- a) **anti-vaxxer**, those who oppose vaccinating people
- b) **pro-vaxxer**, those who support vaccinating people

It is very difficult to tell exactly how many people share each of these views. It is even more difficult to understand all the reasoning why anti-vaxxer opinions are getting more popular.

In the 21st century, social media plays a major role in forming the public opinion. Platforms like Facebook, YouTube, and Twitter [17] are used to spread new ideas and effectively influence the widespread perception of popular topics. In contrast to conventional media (television, newspaper) it is easier for individuals or smaller publishers to reach wide audiences compared to the pre-internet era. Hence it is arguably more difficult to determine what publishers form the public opinion and where they stand on key issues [16].

My thesis focuses on the social media platforms called “Twitter”. Aiming to programmatically identify which tweets have anti-vaccination sentiment and which supports mass vaccination. In order to successfully achieve that several steps need to be completed including the collection of data, preprocessing, encoding, classification, and finally evaluation of the results.

This thesis puts emphasis on testing the viability of encoding methods. These methods are used to associate any real-world object to multidimensional numeric vectors that can be used to train and input into classification algorithms.

The two approaches covered are

- document embedding on the text of the tweets
- graph embedding on the structure of how the users are interacting with each other on Twitter

After multiple data preprocessing steps, several machine learning algorithms were deployed to identify pro-vaxxer or anti-vaxxer content in the collected Twitter data.

1.2 Setting up an environment

It is important to find the right tools to test different algorithms and manipulate data. We have the advantage to be able to use computers. One can use an existing software solution for data processing and analysis or can develop custom tools. If the latter is chosen it is still important not to reinvent the wheel and use already existing implementations wherever possible.

I chose to use Python - more specifically Python 3.6 - for this project.

Python is a popular programming language among researchers and data scientists. It is easy to learn and very versatile. Development with Python is generally fast compared to many other languages, mainly due to its clean syntax and great code readability.

Another very important consideration is the number of available packages dealing with data processing, analysis, machine learning, and other relevant fields. Also, the package manager is built-in so it is very easy to consume these dependencies during development.

Python is an interpreted language which means that lines of the software source code are read, parsed, and executed line-by-line. This makes it slower than compiled languages like C or C++. However, a lot of machine learning and other libraries are written in a way that they utilize a highly optimized native code in the background. This enables them to run computation-intensive parts very efficiently on the CPU or in some cases even on the highly parallel GPU. Therefore the fast development enabled by python can be used with little compromise on performance.

I used Jupyter Notebook framework as a primary development environment. It is an interactive web-based environment that enables to interlace code snippets with its output and at the same time visualize it.

Python ships with its package manager called “pip”. Packages can be installed to extend the functionality to the standard library. Anyone can create and publish a package to a package repository. Python has a default public repository “PyPI.org”. Installing a package is easy, the package manager takes care of installing dependencies and ensuring that the correct version of packages gets installed. In most cases

installing a package can be done by issuing a simple command like the following which installs the latest stable version of the “pandas” package.

```
pip install pandas
```

Some of the notable packages I used are:

- pandas: data reading, filtering
- numpy: fast data manipulation
- emoji: recognizing emojis, replacing with text representation
- nltk: tokenization, stopwords
- sklearn.feature_extraction: TF-IDF encoding
- gensim: doc2vec encoding
- networkx: graph displaying, graph manipulation
- karateclub: graph embedding
- sklearn (scikit-learn): classification models
- sklearn.metrics: evaluation of the classification
- matplotlib.pyplot and seaborn: generating the heatmaps
- wordcloud: generating the wordcloud figures

Chapter 2

Data

Twitter is an American microblogging and social networking service on which users post and interact with messages known as “tweets”. Tweets are restricted to 280 characters. As of 2019, Twitter had more than 330 million monthly active users [4]. The service has an application programming interface (API) that allows other web services and applications to integrate with Twitter.

2.1 Data collection and labeling

The data is collected ¹ from Twitter weekly using Twitter’s API. The API allows requesting specific information from Twitter, and in response returns data that matches the queries. The API has request limits in place in order to provide reliable service to every API user. Limitations apply to the overall amount of queries per 15 minutes, and also on a per-user or per-application basis to different endpoints. Because of these limitations data is continuously collected throughout a week. At the end of each week, the gathered data is appended to all previously collected data then copied to a location from where the programs I wrote for this thesis can work with it.

Only publicly available data - which anyone can view on Twitter - are collected.

In order to find relevant tweets, the following strategy was implemented. Queries made to fetch tweets are based on specific keywords. Hereinafter these tweets going to be referred to as “seeds”. The following keywords were included in the search: “vaccine”, “vaccination”, “vaccinated”, “vaxxer”, “vaxxers”, “#CovidVaccine” and “covid denier”. In an effort to eliminate the potential political biases some keywords are used to exclude tweets that contained them. These were the following: “trump”, “biden”, “republican”, “democrat”.

Tweets with at least 50 replies are collected with all the replies they have. Towards the needed 50 replies not only the immediate replies count but also the replies given to the replies of the tweet.

¹Data collection and a significant part of labeling was done by Ferenc Béres.

More languages were present in the data, but tweets were filtered by language to only keep the ones written in English.

The following attributes are collected from the tweets.

General tweet features:

- tweet id which uniquely identifies the tweet
- the date and the time of posting
- full text of the tweet
- language of the tweet

User related features:

- user id which uniquely identifies the user who posted the tweet
- user screen name by which the user can be searched on Twitter
- location of the user

Reply related features (only present for tweets which are replies):

- the id of the tweet which the tweet is in reply to
- the id of the user who the tweet is in reply to

Data labeling

The end goal of the project is to create a program that can determine the vaccination sentiment of the tweets. The method used to achieve this goal is to use supervised machine learning algorithms. In order to train these algorithms, we need at least some of the data already labeled, meaning that the correct stance on vaccination should be determined and associated with each record. After data collection, labeling was done manually using a custom application made with the Streamlit Python framework.

Summary

A total number of approximately 3 million tweets were collected from January 8 to May 2. From all the tweets 1391 seed tweets were labeled. 300 tweets were identified as having anti-vaxxer sentiment while 1091 had pro-vaxxer sentiment. 229926 more tweets were included in the dataset, these are replies to seeds used with graph embedding.

2.2 Text preprocessing

Goal of text preprocessing is to transform raw text to a format which is better suited for natural language processing, in this case, text classification using document embedding. It is very important to apply the same preprocessing pipeline to the whole dataset. Even if it is separated for example to training and test data preprocessing should be done in the exact same way.

On 2.1 you can see a tweet before and after text preprocessing.

```
Original tweets:
I'm having my Covid vaccine today. I'm v excited. And humbled. And no, I'm not concerned about my
fertility.... 😊

Those who falsely claim Vaccines are 100% safe and who laugh at anti-vaxxers will be dependent on
those who refuse to tell the official lies to say that wide-spread vaccination *is* critical. 23
die in Norway after receiving COVID-19 vaccine: https://t.co/123456 via @nypost

After preprocessing:
covid vaccine today v excited humbled concerned fertility em_face_with_rolling_eyes

falsely claim vaccines onehundred safe laugh antivaxxers dependent refuse tell official lies say
widespread vaccination critical twentythree die norway receiving covid19 vaccine via
```

Figure 2.1: Text preprocessing examples - tweets before and after preprocessing.

Text preprocessing usually consists of three main components: noise removal, tokenization, and normalization.

Noise removal

The purpose of noise removal is to strip the original text of any irrelevant features that will not carry valuable information about what is in question, but can cause the algorithms to be less effective.

The following preprocessing steps were applied to the Twitter dataset.

- Removal of links. Regular expressions were used to match specific patterns, like text starting with “www.” or “https://”.
- Converting hashtags to simple words. In the Twitter application, one can use a hash mark to create a so-called hashtag. These are used by Twitter and the community in different ways, but for our purposes, it is not relevant whether a word appears in a hashtag or in plain text. So leading hash marks are removed, while the text of the hashtag is kept, because it is an organic part of the tweet’s content. (“How to make #money on #Instagram?”)
- In tweets one can mention other users, which can be used for navigation on Twitter. These hold no valuable insight hence removed (Example: @twitter)
- Replace character sequence & - which in tweets is displayed as & sign - with the word “and”.

- Replace contractions in text (she’s - she is, I’ll - I will), it is important to be done before tokenization since tokenizer will split words at whitespaces and non-alphanumerical characters (it would split don’t into “don”, “t” not the appropriate “do”, “not”)
- Replacing emojis with their text representation (<3 → heart)

Tokenization

Tokenization is the process of splitting the text into smaller parts. A function called `word_tokenize` from Natural Language Processing toolkit is used for this task. It splits the text into words, into phrases. First, it tries to split it into sentences then split those into words.

Normalization

Normalization aims to make the words equal from different points of view. Normalization takes place after tokenization. These are the steps that were applied to the tokens.

- Special non-alphanumerical characters were removed. (example £ §)
- All remaining punctuation was removed.
- Empty strings were removed.
- Numbers were converted to their string representation (1. → first, 2 → two)
- All words were converted to lowercase.
- English stopwords like “is”, “you” holds little information, but very frequent in text, so for better results, they were removed.

2.3 Data discovery and visualization

Word frequencies

Wordclouds are great for visualizing text data. Figure 2.2 shows the most representative words in the anti-vaxxer and pro-vaxxer tweets. The relevance of the words is arguably easier perceived when displayed on a wordcloud compared to a table.

The rate at which a given word occurs in tweets is computed for three datasets (all the tweets, anti-vaxxer tweets, and pro-vaxxer tweets). Words with higher occurrence rate in pro- and anti-vaxxer dataset than in the full dataset are collected. Among these, the 50 most frequent are displayed on a respective wordcloud. Emojis are excluded from the wordclouds.

Antivax emojis	Provax emojis
😭 face_with_tears_of_joy	💉 syringe
🩺 syringe	🙏 folded_hands
🤔 thinking_face	🥳 partying_face
🙄 pouting_face	❤️ red_heart
😞 pensive_face	💪 flexed_biceps
🚫 no_entry	👏 clapping_hands
👏 clapping_hands	🎉 party_popper
😓 weary_face	😷 face_with_medical_mask
😱 face_screaming_in_fear	😊 smiling_face_with_smiling_eyes
😡 angry_face	👍 thumbs_up
🙏 folded_hands	✅ check_mark_button
🦠 microbe	❤️ growing_heart
😳 flushed_face	😭 loudly_crying_face
⚪ latin_cross	😊 smiling_face_with_hearts
😓 face_with_rolling_eyes	🦠 microbe
😞 pleading_face	🙌 raising_hands
🙄 woman_shrugging	😊 beaming_face_with_smiling_eyes
😭 crying_face	🐼 seenoevil_monkey
🙄 woman_tipping_hand	😭 face_with_tears_of_joy
🤢 nauseated_face	❤️ two_hearts
😓 anxious_face_with_sweat	👇 backhand_index_pointing_down
👉 middle_finger	🦋 butterfly
💀 skull	🚓 police_car_light
😊 beaming_face_with_smiling_eyes	😊 grinning_face_with_smiling_eyes
😞 confused_face	🌷 tulip
👇 backhand_index_pointing_down	➡️ right_arrow
🐼 seenoevil_monkey	🙌 crossed_fingers
😞 frowning_face	💙 blue_heart

Figure 2.3: Top emojis for anti-vaxxer and pro-vaxxer tweets in decreasing order of usage

Chapter 3

Document Encoding

Machine learning algorithms are only able to handle numeric values. Therefore textual data first have to be transformed into a numeric representation like multidimensional vectors. This process is called document embedding, document encoding, or in some cases text vectorization. It is important to use a method that preserves as much semantic information as possible while transforming text into a vector space. Text preprocessing steps are always performed before applying vectorization.

3.1 TF-IDF vectorization

Term frequency – inverse document frequency abbreviated as TF-IDF is a numerical statistic that is intended to measure the importance of a word in a document while also considering the importance of the word in the context of all documents. The vectorization technique described in this chapter is based on this metric.

In this case, document is referring to the text content of an individual tweet. Corpus is the collection of all documents.

It is normally computed as follows [23]. Suppose we have a corpus consisting of N documents. Define f_{ij} to be the frequency (number of occurrences) of term (word) i in document j . Then, define the term frequency TF_{ij} to be:

$$TF_{ij} = \frac{f_{ij}}{\max_k f_{kj}} \quad (3.1)$$

That is, the term frequency of term i in document j is f_{ij} normalized by dividing it by the maximum number of occurrences of any term in the same document. Thus, the most frequent term in document j gets a TF of 1, and other terms get fractions as their term frequency for this document.

The IDF for a term is defined as follows. Suppose term i appears in n_i of the N documents in the collection.

$$IDF_i = \log_2 \frac{N}{n_i} \quad (3.2)$$

Then TF-IDF metric for term i in document j is then defined to be $TF_{ij} \times IDF_i$

Vectorization

First a vocabulary is constructed from all the terms in the entire corpus. In this mapping, each term is assigned an index in the vector. The vectors dimension is equal to the size of the vocabulary. In order to spare resources the maximum number of terms in the vocabulary is limited to a number k . Terms are ordered in descending order by the number of times they appear in the corpus, and only the top k terms are kept.

Then for each document a vector is created in which each item is equal to the TF-IDF score of the corresponding term from the vocabulary.

Python implementation

The implementation which I used is slightly different than previously described. It is part of the scikit-learn library [3]. Its implementation normalizes vectors instead of normalizing the TF-IDF score. The TF-IDF score is calculated as follows

The TF is simply the number of times a term occurs in a document.

$$TF_{ij} = f_{ij} \quad (3.3)$$

The IDF calculation is also a bit different. It prevents zero division in certain circumstances.

$$IDF_i = \log \frac{1 + N}{1 + n_i} + 1 \quad (3.4)$$

The resulting TF-IDF vectors are then normalized by the Euclidean norm.

$$v_{norm} = \frac{v}{\|v\|_2} = \frac{v}{\sqrt{v_1^2 + v_2^2 + \dots + v_n^2}} \quad (3.5)$$

Motivation behind using TF-IDF for vectorization

The weight of a term that occurs in a document is simply proportional to the term frequency. Which is responsible for giving more weight to words that are used more.

The specificity of a term can be quantified as an inverse function of the number of documents in which it occurs. It helps to assign low scores to unimportant words and higher to rare ones.

TF-IDF vectorization does completely ignore the order of terms within a document. Which in some cases can be an issue. It can be improved by instead of using individual words as terms, multiple consecutive words (so-called n-grams) can be used as terms. Although it introduces other issues, like it yields a sparse vector and requires significantly more memory.

3.2 Doc2Vec

Doc2Vec is a commonly used name for a document embedding algorithm developed by Quoc Le and Tomas Mikolov in 2014 [18]. It is an unsupervised algorithm that generates vectors for paragraphs - variable length sections - of a corpus. Its focus is to generate vectors in a way that paragraphs with similar content are closer in the vector space.

It works on a similar principle as an algorithm developed earlier and commonly referred to as Word2Vec, which generates vectors for words [20]. First I focus on this method.

Simpler algorithms like one-hot-encoding for words or bag-of-words for documents (paragraphs) are practically ignoring syntactic and semantic information. This means that for example words “Apple”, “Potato” and “Ocean” all have the same relation to each other. Word2Vec solves this problem and generates vectors that are more similar if the words are more similar from a point of view. Furthermore, it has been demonstrated that using this technique more complex analogies can be computed by simple vector algebra. For example $\text{vector}(\text{“King”}) - \text{vector}(\text{“Man”}) + \text{vector}(\text{“Woman”}) = \text{vector}(\text{“Queen”})$.

This method utilizes a neural network consisting of three layers. An input layer, a projection layer, and an output layer. The weight matrix in the input layer is shared between all input words and the output layer. Two different approaches are proposed. Either the network is trained to predict a word based on its context this is called “Continuous Bag-of-Words” model, or to predict multiple words (a context) based on a single word, this is the “Continuous Skip-gram” model.

In the case of the former the input layer receives vectors representing the preceding N words, and the following (future) N words. N should be chosen considering that a large N results in more complexity and training time, but can yield better results. A log-linear classifier is used to predict the word in question. The network’s layout is shown in figure 3.1. Training is done using stochastic gradient descent and back-propagation. At every iteration, a word is chosen randomly from the corpus and its context is used as input for the network.

In case of the Continuous Skip-gram model input is a single word and the aim of the neural network is to predict the neighborhood of the word. This model performs better in some tests if the neighborhood is chosen to be large enough in the training. However, it is slower to train.

Figure 3.1: CBOW and Skip-gram model

Doc2Vec is based on the same idea as Word2Vec. The key difference is that it tries to separate the information about the immediate context of a word and “something” that is a wider context and specific to a paragraph (document inside the corpus). It achieves that by introducing a vector describing a paragraph called paragraph id. Then the neural network is modified so that during training the paragraph vector of the chosen word is also given as input, and modifications are applied via gradient descent and backpropagation. This method is called Paragraph Vector - Distributed Memory and is illustrated in figure 3.2.

Figure 3.2: Paragraph Vector - Distributed Memory

Another variant is proposed in the paper, which is analogous to the Skip-gram version of Word2Vec. It only receives the paragraph id as an input and predicts multiple words from the paragraph. During training, a random word is always chosen from the paragraph for feedback. This is shown in figure 3.3.

Figure 3.3: Paragraph Vector - Distributed Bag of Words

The inventors of this method propose that the two variants can be used in combination, to achieve more consistent results. However, PV-DM in itself can yield very impressive results when used for sentiment analysis [19]. The Python implementation I used uses PV-DM on its own [1].

Chapter 4

Graph Embedding

Graph embedding methods are used to transform graphs, nodes, edges into a lower-dimensional vector space while preserving the largest amount of structural information possible. This in practice means that homomorph graphs or graphs with little differences (only a few edges or nodes added or deleted) should have vectors that are close in the vector space, while large differences should result in the vectors being farther apart.

The idea behind using graph embedding for vaccine sentiment analysis is that the way we use social media and the clustering of similar opinions and the number of interactions between similarly thinking individuals possibly reveal information about the individuals attitude toward some popular topics including vaccination.

The text of the tweet does not contain any information about the users' connections. However during data collection if a tweet is a response to another one that connection is stored. It is later used to build a graph. It is expected that the structure of this graph could be used to predict the vaccine sentiment of the seed in the graph (the first tweet posted). For example, it is possible that anti-vaxxer tweets generate more debate than pro-vaxxer ones.

An example can be seen in figure 4.1, where node 1 is a seed tweet which means it is not a response to any other tweet. Many response tweets can be seen connected to this seed tweet directly. Some tweets are responses to other responses meaning they don't have an immediate connection to the initial seed tweet. The longest such chain contains 4 nodes in this example ending on node 54.

Figure 4.1: Example for a seed tweet’s connection graph

4.1 Graph2Vec

Graph2Vec is a graph embedding method. It generates a fixed height vector representation for a graph with any number of nodes. Graph2Vec is based on the Doc2Vec skip-gram version algorithm.

The idea behind its development that similar to how a document is a set of words, a graph is a set of subgraphs.

In figure 4.2 the following similarity between doc2vec and graph2vec can be observed:

- a) doc2vec’s skip-gram model - Given a document d , it samples c words from d and considers them as co-occurring in the same context (i.e., context of document d) uses them to learn d ’s representation.
- b) graph2vec - Given a graph G , it samples c rooted subgraphs around different nodes that occur in G and uses them analogous to doc2vec’s context words and thus learns G ’s representation. [21]

Figure 4.2: Doc2vec and graph2vec skip-gram model

The Python implementation [2] I used assumes the following about the graphs [25]

- The graph is undirected.
- The graph consists of one connected component.
- Node numbering starts from 0 and increasing continuously.
- The graph cannot contain loops or multiple edges.

This holds true to the graph constructed from the tweets.

Chapter 5

Classification

The vaccination sentiment classification problem is a binary classification problem, there are two classes: anti-vaxxer and pro-vaxxer. The goal of a classification algorithm is to place new unlabeled tweets into the proper class without human oversight.

In the following subchapters, I present briefly the algorithms which were used in the evaluations of the embeddings.

5.1 Baseline classifiers

Some of the metrics that can measure how different classifier algorithms perform are best describe the performance in relation to other classifiers. In order to get a baseline measurement, trivial classification algorithms can be used. These simple solutions are easy to understand and implement. Because of the way they constructed a judgment can be made about other algorithms based on how much they outperform these basic algorithms.

The following algorithms were implemented to give a baseline metric for classification wellness:

1. “most frequent” - this algorithm will always predict the label that is the most frequent in training data
2. “uniform” - this algorithm will choose a prediction uniformly randomly from all the possible predictions

5.2 K-Nearest Neighbors

Nearest Neighbors classification [11] is set of algorithms. They work on the same principle but a constant K determines how many neighbors they take into account when computing predictions.

The prediction is computed by finding K elements in the training data set nearest to the element in question. Then the prediction will be the most frequent class in

the aforementioned subset. This is analogous to simple majority voting. It could be further tuned by assigning different weights to each vote for example by the distance from the sample in question.

In the context of this algorithm nearest is defined as the minimal distance of the vector representation of the data samples. The distance is the Minkowski distance of the two vectors.

$$d(x, y) = \left(\sum_{i=1}^n |x_i - y_i|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \quad (5.1)$$

Minkowski distance in case of $p = 2$ equivalent to the Euclidean distance of the N-dimensional vectors.

For the evaluation of this algorithm, I used $K = 5$.

5.3 Random forest

Random forest [8] is a supervised ensemble machine learning algorithm. Ensemble learning means that the learning algorithm uses multiple simpler algorithms for prediction and takes average (in case of a regression problem) or outputs the class which the most smaller algorithms predicted (in case of a classification problem). Random forest consists of many decision trees.

Decision trees are simple learning algorithms consisting of simple decision rules put into a tree structure. In case of classification, the leaves of the tree represent the different classes. The decision tree starts out from a single node and then iteratively splits every node by the most important feature. This process is done until a desired depth of the tree is reached or every node is pure meaning when following the rules of the tree the records in a leaf are from the same class.

The trees in the random forest split differently, instead of finding the most important feature from all the features, it finds the most important feature from a random subset of features, hence the “random” in the naming.

The advantage of using random forest over a decision tree is that the prediction will be more accurate and stable.

5.4 Neural Network

Neural network (neural net) [14] is a collection of connected nodes inspired by the neurons in a biological brain. In this thesis multilayer perceptron is used which is a class of neural networks. It consists of three types of layer of nodes: an input layer, hidden layers, and an output layer. Excluding the input nodes, each node has a nonlinear activation function (sigmoid function is often used). Each edge in the

network has a weight. An algorithm called backpropagation computes the gradient of the loss function with respect to the weights of the network.

Sigmoid function:

$$S(x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-x}} = \frac{e^x}{e^x + 1} \quad (5.2)$$

5.5 Bernoulli Naive Bayes

Bernoulli Naive Bayes is a variant of Naive Bayes [27]. Naive Bayes is a classification algorithm based on Bayes theorem which gives the likelihood of occurrence of the event. The “naive” name hints at the assumption of conditional independence between every pair of features given the value of the class variable. Bernoulli Naive Bayes expects binary features, since the features in our data are not binary, the classifier transforms them into binary with 0 as the threshold. Bernoulli Naive Bayes Classifier is based on the following rule:

$$P(x_i | y) = P(i | y)x_i + (1 - P(i | y))(1 - x_i) \quad (5.3)$$

5.6 Logistic Regression

Logistic Regression [10] contrary to its name is a supervised classification algorithm. Data is fit into a linear regression model then a logistic function is applied hence the name logistic regression.

It can be used in binary classification problems. A threshold is set to predict which class the data instance belongs to.

Chapter 6

Evaluation

Each embedding method was evaluated using the following evaluation process:

1. The embeddings are created using the embedding algorithm for different embedding dimensions. The three different embedding methods are TF-IDF, doc2vec, and graph2vec. The same dimensions were used in case the document embedding methods and a different dimension list in case of graph2vec.
2. The embedded vectors in a given dimension are split into train and test set using cross-validation.
3. For each train-test set in the cross-validation, all the classification algorithms are applied.
4. The classifications are evaluated using an evaluation metric.
5. A heatmap was generated from the dimensions and the evaluated classifications to compare the different embeddings with each other.

6.1 Evaluation metrics

Evaluation metrics [15] are used to measure the performance of a machine learning algorithm. The following evaluation metrics were considered:

- P - Number of positive records
- N - Number of negative records
- TP - Number of True Positives: positive records classified properly
- TN - Number of True Negatives: negative records classified properly
- FP - Number of False Positives: negative records classified as positive
- FN - Number of False Negatives: positive records classified as negative
- accuracy: $\frac{TP+TN}{P+N}$

- error rate = 1–accuracy
- precision (specificity): $\frac{TP}{TP+FP}$
- recall (sensitivity) = True positive rate (TPR): $\frac{TP}{TP+FN}$
- FPT = False positive rate = $\frac{FP}{FP+TN}$

F1-score of F-measure is the harmonic mean of the precision and recall, therefore combining both into one metric.

$$F_1 = 2 \cdot \frac{\text{precision} \cdot \text{recall}}{\text{precision} + \text{recall}} \quad (6.1)$$

ROC curve plots the true positive rates against the false positive rates, showing the performance of the classification model at different classification thresholds.

AUC (or ROC-AUC score) [13] is a metric closely connected to the ROC curve, as it is the area under the roc curve. It ranges from 0 to 1, a perfect model, which classifies everything correctly all the time has an AUC score of 1.

6.2 Data imbalance

The dataset used in this thesis is imbalanced because the distribution of tweets is not equal across the classes, the majority of tweets belong to the pro-vaccine class. The ratio of pro-vaxxer to anti-vaxxer tweets is 4:1.

The usual metrics with the goodness of a classification is measured is accuracy or error rate.

Unfortunately, accuracy and error rate are less useful in the case of imbalanced classes [7]. The following example illustrates this: imagine a dataset where the labels are binary, and from every 100 records only one belongs to the minority class. If we have a simple classifier, which for every record only predicts the majority label then we will have a classifier with 0.99 accuracy. In this case, we would not say that this is a great classifier for the problem even though the accuracy score suggests otherwise. (The same is true for error rate.)

The AUC score is slightly better, but the class imbalance still strongly impacts it. Better metrics for imbalanced classification are precision, recall, and F1-score.

Figure 6.1: TF-IDF embedding evaluated with F1-score (left) and ROC-AUC score (right)

While testing the metrics the ROC-AUC score had a high score in every case where the F1-score was high, but not in reverse. This can be observed in figure 6.1, on the heatmaps of the TF-IDF embedding evaluated by these two metrics. This was due to the fact that the ROC-AUC score is more skewed by the class imbalance than the F1-score. Therefore the best metrics for this task turned out to be the F1-score.

6.3 Cross-validation

Cross-validation [6] is a resampling procedure used to evaluate machine learning models on a limited data sample. In k -fold cross-validation, the data is divided into k subsets. Each one of the k subsets is used as the test set and the other $k - 1$ subset are used combined as the training set. After computing the used metrics k times the results are averaged.

The advantage to this method is it matters less how exactly the data is divided into train and test set. Cross-validation gives greater confidence in the results since it is the making predictions and testing the classifiers on the whole data.

In this thesis 5-fold cross-validation was used to evaluate the classifications.

Chapter 7

Results

7.1 Document encodings evaluation

The two document encoding algorithms were evaluated exactly the same way, so comparison between the two is possible.

In table 7.1 we can observe that the doc2vec embedding takes approximately 1000 times amount of runtime to generate the embedding than the TF-IDF method. Also notable difference that while with the TF-IDF embedding the runtime does not change with changing the embedding dimension, the doc2vec embedding runtime grows as a function of the dimension.

	5	10	20	50	100	200	500	1000	1500	2000
tf-idf	0.13	0.12	0.15	0.11	0.12	0.13	0.15	0.14	0.11	0.15
doc2vec	98.22	97.70	100.00	104.96	103.48	103.84	111.89	123.54	138.66	159.23

Table 7.1: Time (in sec) comparison of the embeddings by embedding dimension

Tf-idf does not takes word order into account, “The quick brown fox jumps over a lazy dog.” has the same embedding as “The lazy brown dog jumps over a quick fox.” While with the doc2vec encoding the word order influences the embedding so the two example sentence results in two different embeddings.

On the following two figures (7.2 and 7.1) the differences between the classifications can be observed. The classifiers have different results depending on the embedding algorithm. The Logistic Regression is a good classification method in case of the doc2vec encoding but with the TF-IDF it gives the poorest result of the five classifiers. The Neural Net and the Bernoulli Naive Bayes are good classifiers in both cases.

Figure 7.1: TF-IDF embedding evaluated with F-score using different vector dimensions and classifiers

Figure 7.2: Doc2vec embedding evaluated with F-score using different vector dimensions and classifiers

While the TF-IDF method needs larger embedding dimensions (larger than 100), the doc2vec gives good prediction even with the 10-dimensional embedding. The TF-IDF is bad for small dimensions since in this case, the vector dimension is equal to the used vocabulary size and if only a small portion of the words are used, then the performance of the embedding gets worse.

In case of the TF-IDF, the predictions are getting better with increasing the embedding dimension, then start to get worse. Embedding dimensions matter less to the doc2vec algorithm, therefore getting more similar embedding scores across all the different dimensions.

The overall predictive power of the encodings is the greatest when using TF-IDF encoding with 1000-1500 vector dimension. The best encoding for small storage or small vector dimensions is the Doc2Vec encoding with vector dimension 10.

7.2 Graph embedding evaluation

The different seed graph sizes are displayed in the following 7.3 histogram. Only the lower 95% of the sizes are used because the top 5% covers a really large range (the largest graph size is 5831) therefore they were not displayed on the histogram for better data visibility.

Figure 7.3: Histogram of seed graph sizes

The graph embedding had significantly less predictive power compared to the document embedding methods. The baseline (dummy) classifiers were placed on the heatmap to help the comparison.

Figure 7.4: Graph2vec embedding evaluated with F-score using different vector dimensions and classifiers

The graph embedding only had slight predicting power in the classification but it is significant (not due to random chance). The F1-scores of the classifications are not or only marginally better than the baseline classifiers. This is probably due to the fact that the graphs are really similar to each other, each star-shaped with only a few nodes hanging on the side. There are also significant size differences between the graphs.

Chapter 8

Conclusion

In this thesis I introduced the task of collecting and analyzing publicly available Twitter data to get information about sentiment towards vaccination. Then the method of collecting data and labeling is discussed. The need for and the implemented steps of text preprocessing are also demonstrated.

The main focus of this work was to cover two different approaches of transforming structural data into vector space, which can then be used for classification. The first of these was encoding of text content of the tweets. Two algorithms were used for this task TF-IDF vectorization and Doc2Vec. The other approach used a graph constructed from tweets as nodes and edges as the connection between tweets and their replies, then the Graph2Vec algorithm was used to transform it to a vector space.

Multiple classification algorithms were introduced, these were used to predict the vaccine sentiment of a tweet. Then the methodology for comparing and evaluating the performance of different encoding methods combined with each classification algorithms was covered, before the inclusion of detailed results of the experiments.

8.1 Limitations

The following limitations were observed:

- Twitter tries to remove strongly anti-vaxxer content and misinformation from its platform, so the anti-vaxxer tweets in the data might not be representative for the population.
- Due to the API limits the size of the data is limited to approximately 1000 seeds and their replies per week.
- Size of labeled training data is small. Due to labeling done by hand, not all of the dataset are labeled, unsupervised methods could be used to deal with the unlabeled data.
- The used document embedding methods cannot detect sarcasm and jokes in the tweets which are frequently used.

- There is bias in the data due to the specified keywords in the data collection.
- The classification was binary so only trained for two labels anti-vaxxer and pro-vaxxer therefore neutral opinions will have to be classified as one of them.

8.2 Future research

Three main ideas arise at the end of this thesis where the work could be expanded.

Random resampling

Random resampling could fix the imbalance problems in the data. Random under or oversampling or a mix of the two could be used.

Random undersampling removes random instances from the majority class. The advantage of this method is no duplicate data, the drawback is that it loses information of the discarded data, and the size of the dataset is reduced significantly.

Random oversampling duplicates random instances from the minority class. The advantage of this method is that no information is lost and the dataset is not reduced in size, the disadvantage that there will be duplicates in the data.

Classification using three classes

Currently the binary classification does not allow neutral opinions, every tweet is classified as either pro-vaxxer or anti-vaxxer content. Introducing a neutral option could make the predictions better. The anti-vaxxer content could be targeted more specifically.

Node2vec encoding

Since the graph embedding does not resulted in much success, another embedding type could be used. Node2vec [12] encoding could be applied to the users of the whole user-user graph, where two users are connected if one of them replied to the other's tweet or they both replied to the same tweet. Or we can use similar walk-based embedding methods including Deepwalk [22] and LINE [26].

Other embedding methods can also be applied, for example, GraRep [9] can represent multi-hop neighborhood similarity, while Diff2Vec [24] can preserve distances between nodes by sampling diffusion trees during the training process. On the other hand, Role2Vec [5], a structural node embedding method assigns similar vectors to two addresses if they have similar motif structure in the transaction graph despite their distance in the network, several of these methods implemented as a Python package [25].

Acknowledgements

The COVID data collection was supported by the Ministry of Innovation and Technology NRDI Office within the framework of the Artificial Intelligence National Laboratory Program.

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